

Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) in Indonesian Sentences Using Simplified Lesk Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

The Indonesian language contains several words with inherent ambiguity, meaning they possess more than one possible interpretation. Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD), a branch of Natural Language Processing (NLP), deals with the challenge of resolving this ambiguity and identifying the precise meaning of a word based on its context. Among the algorithms used for WSD, the Simplified Lesk algorithm stands out as particularly popular. To assess its effectiveness, tests were conducted using the Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI) as a reference for word definitions, and a dataset of 300 Indonesian sentences containing ambiguous words and their respective meanings as determined by human perception. The research reveals that the configuration of the preprocessing phase plays a crucial role in accurately identifying the intended meaning. After evaluation, the overall accuracy achieved was 58% for the dataset, incorporating preprocessing techniques such as stemming and stopword.

Keywords :Ambiguous, Natural Language Processing ,Word Sense Disambiguation, Simplified Lesk

1. Introduction

The presence of ambiguous words in the Indonesian language can make the meaning of a sentence unclear or confusing. This poses a challenge, as human perception has the linguistic ability to easily determine the correct meaning of ambiguous words based on context. **Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD)** is a subfield of Natural Language Processing (NLP) that aims to computationally identify the exact meaning of words based on their context [1].

A knowledge-based approach to WSD includes methods like the Lesk algorithm, which is widely used for its simple mechanism and ability to effectively handle polysemous words. There are two well-known variations of the Lesk algorithm: **Original Lesk** and **Simplified Lesk**. The Simplified Lesk algorithm is preferred due to its faster execution, lower computational time complexity, and higher accuracy in distinguishing word meanings compared to the Original Lesk algorithm [2]. Therefore, this study applies the Simplified Lesk algorithm to the task of WSD in Indonesian sentences.

2. Literature Study

This chapter provides a literature review that forms the foundation of this research, covering **Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD)**, the **Simplified Lesk Algorithm**, and **Evaluation Metrics**.

2.1. Word Sense Disambiguation

Lexical ambiguity occurs when a single word has multiple meanings. Resolving this ambiguity, known as **Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD)**, can improve various fields such as **Machine Translation, Parsing, Natural Language Understanding (NLU)**, and **lexicography** [3]. WSD is a subfield of NLP in which computer systems are designed to identify the correct meaning of a word in a specific context [4]. The WSD problem involves two main challenges: first, representing the different meanings of a word so an algorithm can interpret them, and second, determining which meaning fits the word's context [5].

2.2. Preprocessing

The preprocessing phase begins with **tokenization**, the process of breaking text into meaningful elements like words, phrases, and symbols [7]. This is followed by **stopword removal**, which eliminates irrelevant words, and **stemming**, which normalizes words to their base form [6]. The implementation of stemming and stopword removal can significantly influence the performance of a WSD system [8]. Stemming ensures that morphologically different forms of a word are treated as the same content word, while stopword removal prevents the content word matrix from becoming too sparse and eliminates unimportant words.

2.3. Simplified Lesk Algorithm

The Lesk algorithm, published in 1986, is one of the earliest and most popular algorithms that use a machine-readable dictionary. The algorithm works by measuring the overlap between word sense definitions in a given context [9]. The **Simplified Lesk algorithm** is a variation of this approach. It runs a separate WSD process for each ambiguous word in the input text. The correct sense for each word is determined by finding the sense with the greatest overlap between its dictionary definition and the current context [10]. The process flow of the Simplified Lesk algorithm is illustrated in Fig. 1.

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function Simplified_Lesk(word, sentence)
  best-sense ← most frequent sense for word
  max-overlap ← 0
  context ← set of words in sentence
  for each sense in senses of word do
    signature ← set of words in the gloss. examples of sense
    overlap ← Compute_overlap(signature, context)
    if overlap > max-overlap then
      max-overlap ← overlap
      best-sense ← sense
  end
  return(best-sense) { returns best sense of word }

```

Fig. 1. Simplified Lesk Process (Aliwy & Abbas, 2015)

Before the algorithm is executed, sentences are preprocessed to generate a context. The input ambiguous word is then used to look up its definitions in a dictionary. The dictionary definitions (glosses) for all the possible meanings are examined, and the algorithm calculates the number of common words shared between the context and the gloss of each meaning [11]. The meaning with the highest number of overlapping words is considered the most appropriate sense [12].

2.4. Evaluation Metric

The standard evaluation method for WSD algorithms is the "exact match" criterion [13]. This method calculates overall accuracy by dividing the number of correctly predicted sense instances by the total number of instances [14]. A correct prediction is one where the predicted sense matches the true sense. The formula for calculating accuracy is:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of True Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Instance}} \quad (1)$$

Based on Equation (1), the "Number of Correct Predictions" refers to the instances where the algorithm correctly predicts the word sense, and the "Total Number of Instances" represents the total number of instances or examples used for evaluation. The higher the accuracy, the better the performance of the WSD algorithm in correctly identifying the appropriate word sense in the given context.

3. Methodology

3.1. Data Collection

This study uses 300 secondary data points. This dataset includes 140 sentences with ambiguous Indonesian words from a scientific publication's test data. An additional 160 sentences were collected from various official articles, with the ambiguous words chosen according to the required criteria. The **Actual Sense** data was determined independently by human perception, selecting the most appropriate meaning from a dictionary that corresponded to the sentence's context.

3.2. System Architecture

The overall architecture of the WSD system is shown in Fig. 2. The process of building the system with the Simplified Lesk algorithm goes through several stages.

Fig. 2. WSD Architecture System

First, the **preprocessing** stage prepares the data. The ambiguous words in the sentences are identified as target words. Then, their multiple meanings are retrieved from a dictionary to find the most appropriate meaning based on the sentence's context. Each word's meaning is processed by calculating the overlap between the meaning and the context. The system selects the meaning with the highest overlap as the predicted meaning that matches the ambiguous word.

4. Result and Discussion

The testing involved four scenarios using 300 data points consisting of Indonesian sentences, ambiguous words, and the corresponding Actual Sense to generate context for determining the appropriate meaning. The WSD process was tested with the following preprocessing approaches: (1) stemming, (2) stopword removal, (3) both stemming and stopword removal, and (4) no preprocessing, i.e., without stemming or stopword removal. Based on the experimental configuration results, an analysis was conducted to calculate accuracy using the evaluation metrics.

Each scenario was evaluated to determine the effectiveness and impact of the preprocessing steps on the WSD results. By comparing the outcomes, the study aimed to identify the most suitable preprocessing approach that yields the best WSD performance for the dataset. Figure 3 presents a comparison of the accuracy results obtained from each scenario, serving as the basis for selecting the best process for WSD using the Simplified Lesk algorithm in Indonesian sentences..

Fig. 3. Scenario Result Comparison

Based on the accuracy comparison shown in Fig. 3, the best process for generating context and determining the correct sense is preprocessing with stemming and stopword removal, which achieved the highest accuracy of 58% across all tested data. Therefore, this experimental configuration is identified as the most effective approach for implementing WSD using the Simplified Lesk algorithm.

Table 1 presents five sample results of WSD using the Simplified Lesk algorithm, along with explanations indicating whether the predicted meanings match the actual meanings. An additional analysis is then conducted for cases where the predicted meanings differ from the actual meanings. Table 1. Sample Result of WSD Using Simplified Lesk

NO	WORD	SENTENCE	<i>ACTUAL SENSE</i>	<i>PREDICTED SENSE</i>	EXPLANATION
1	tahu	Paman membawa banyak oleh-oleh makanan, yang paling terkenal adalah tahu sumedang	makanan dari kedelai putih yang digiling halus-halus, direbus, dan dicetak	kenal (akan); mengenal	Not Match
2	halaman	Halaman yang indah menjadi idaman setiap orang yang punya rumah	pekarangan rumah (sekolah dan sebagainya); tanah di sekitar rumah (sekolah dan sebagainya)	pekarangan rumah (sekolah dan sebagainya); tanah di sekitar rumah (sekolah dan sebagainya)	Match
3	genting	Saat kau ingin rumahmu terang alami, pakailah genting kaca di	tutup atap rumah yang terbuat dari tanah liat yang dicetak dan dibakar,	tutup atap rumah yang terbuat dari tanah liat yang dicetak dan dibakar,	Match

		bagian tertentu atap rumahmu	bermacam- macam bentuknya	bermacam- macam bentuknya	
4	bunga	Setiap tahun, ani menerima bunga 5 persen dari bank	imbalan jasa untuk penggunaan uang atau modal yang dibayar pada waktu tertentu berdasarkan ketentuan atau kesepakatan, umumnya dinyatakan sebagai persentase dari modal pokok	bagian tumbuhan yang akan menjadi buah, biasanya elok warnanya dan harum baunya; kembang	Not Match
5	babak	Risqi Aris babak belur dihajar oleh tetangganya	lecet (tentang kulit)	bagian besar dalam suatu drama atau lakon (terdiri atas beberapa adegan)	Not Match

Based on the results in Table 1, two main factors may have contributed to the incorrect predictions of the actual meanings. First, the lack of overlapping meanings with the context could be due to incomplete context generation and limited dictionary data, reducing the number of overlaps between the meanings and the context. Second, the selection of a meaning among candidates with the same level of overlap is not always accurate, as it tends to prioritize the first encountered meaning, which may not be the most appropriate for the context. To improve the accuracy of the WSD system using the Simplified Lesk algorithm, efforts should focus on expanding the dataset, enhancing the dictionary with more comprehensive word meanings, and optimizing the selection process to better identify the most suitable meaning. Additionally, integrating more sophisticated algorithms or incorporating advanced machine learning techniques could further enhance the system's overall performance.

5. Conclusion

The disambiguation of word meanings using the Simplified Lesk algorithm achieved an accuracy of 58%, which is relatively low and largely influenced by the quality of the data. The limited amount of contextual information and the lack of comprehensive word meanings in the dictionary contributed to this reduced accuracy, making it difficult for the system to identify the appropriate meanings effectively. To improve the accuracy of the WSD system, it is essential to develop a more extensive and comprehensive dataset that provides richer contextual information and includes complete word meanings in the dictionary, ensuring better identification of ambiguous words. The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the

current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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